

Keywords:

#EOOSCMarketplace, #Interdisciplinary,
#Integration, #FinancialSustainability,
#ResearchCollaboration #FAIRPrinciples

Connecting Disciplines: Strengthening Open Data Practices in the EOOSC Marketplace

A Journey of Integration and Collaboration at Gdańsk University of Technology

The service provider

GDANŃSK UNIVERSITY
OF TECHNOLOGY

The project "Data practices in an interdisciplinary perspective - building good standards and universal solutions" was supported under RDA Open Call for Cross-Disciplinary Science Adoption Grants #2 and implemented at Gdańsk University of Technology from January 2023 until July 2023. One of the main objectives was to prepare and implement our existing institutional data repository (MOST WIEDZY Open Research Data Catalogue) and subject repository (Digital Pathology) into the EOOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace as a data provider.

The Challenge

The primary technical and business challenge we faced was the registration of Gdańsk Tech as a Resource Provider on the EOOSC Marketplace Portal which took time and effort. As the library team manages institutional repositories, many other stakeholders (such as IT specialists) are involved in the operating services at the University. Therefore, the library team could not complete the application independently, and the process needed formal approval from the top-level university authorities. Another setback in registering our services was due to the nature of the repository. As MOST Wiedzy performs the function of a data repository, as well as a publications repository, and digital tissues repository, we had to register all services separately.

Magdalena Szuflińska- Żurawska

Head of the Open Science
Competence Center at Gdańsk
University of Technology

"The successful approval of the application submitted by the MOST Wiedzy Open Research Data Catalog for inclusion in the EOOSC Marketplace signifies the catalog's adherence to the EOOSC Marketplace's stringent criteria, including comprehensive documentation of research datasets and compliance with the FAIR principles."

The solution

To expedite the registration process, we sought assistance from the portal administrators, whose help was paramount. We also found the materials in the EOOSC Providers Hub to be of excellent use. We used several EOOSC resources and documentation, including: Information about EOOSC Profiles (<https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub/what-are-eosc-profiles>); Overview of the Onboarding Process (<https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub/how-become-eosc-provider/how-become-eosc-provider-a-general-overview>); Integration handbook for service providers (<https://zenodo.org/record/3826907>). Considering the possible scenarios to ensure optimal and systematic data flow to the EOOSC Marketplace from the MOST Wiedzy Open Research Data Catalog, we decided to implement the integration process with the OpenAIRE service, which serves as a gateway to the EOOSC Marketplace. As Librarians, we utilized several EOOSC resources. We do appreciate and recommend the Train-the-Trainer: An active learning course on understanding & using EOOSC - <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=52101431>.

The user community

Our community consists mainly of researchers, students and doctoral students from Gdańsk University of Technology, as well as scholars from other higher-education institutions. Regarding our registration process, our experience may be helpful for any new candidates in the onboarding process.

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Useful tips & tricks

When registering, the first step should be to familiarise yourself with the materials and documentation prepared by the EOSC team. It could also be helpful to consult the providers who have already completed the process and share their know-how with the potential candidates. What is worth remembering is that the registration process for most providers consists of two stages: registration as a provider and registration of services. Moreover, looking back at our experience, the onboarding process would have been much easier if we had already been registered in OpenAIRE.

The impact on society

The successful approval of the application submitted by the MOST Wiedzy Open Research Data Catalog for inclusion in the EOSC Marketplace signifies the catalog's adherence to the EOSC Marketplace's stringent criteria, including comprehensive documentation of research datasets and compliance with the FAIR principles. One of the key benefits is the worldwide visibility of the resources, which may lead to networking and potential research collaborations between different institutions. We wanted to make our services more visible to the international community and, at the same time, introduce and allow our researchers to access global resources quickly and efficiently. Registering as a provider is crucial for sharing metadata about datasets deposited in our institutional repository. It might also be helpful during training courses and lectures for PhD students. Active participation in the onboarding process strengthened the library's role at the university.

Why do I need EOSC?

The environment offered boosts the visibility and accessibility of the data, making it easier to share and collaborate with other institutions. The significance of EOSC Marketplace lies in the fact that it is a connector with other services. Its users gain access to information about providers, their resources, affiliations, and infrastructure.

Useful material related to this story

RDA - Data practices in an interdisciplinary perspective

Why do I need RDA?

As an independent, global platform RDA provides a forum and inclusive mindset to share experiences, discover and provide knowledge, and showcase a broad range of research data and infrastructure. RDA also covers aspects of the existing standards landscape and detailed issue statements of daily scientific tasks. Personally, I've received several supporting actions from RDA, like the RDA Adoption Stories, Bloggs, Webinars, as well as the Plenary stage, which helps my team get involved and take these benefits back to our "small" but growing community in Poland.

Across disciplines

EOSC Marketplace links providers from different disciplines and countries who may become potential partners in research activities. Access to their resources and services may facilitate cross-disciplinary research initiatives and might be of great significance when promoting the idea of Open Science, tutoring and preparing training materials.

Future developments

The registration in the EOSC Marketplace will facilitate the further development of MOST Wiedzy, expedite our services' indexation process, and allow us to obtain the recognized repository certificates. Our further challenge will be to popularise the EOSC among the academic community at our institution and country. It can only be done with a deep knowledge of the services offered by Marketplace (such as user dashboard, monitoring, or accounting).

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

We will work with our university's vision and aims and then see how different activities related to Open Science could be funded.

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